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Equity and Inclusion

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Abstract

There is a need to enhance the student's capabilities to build a developed nation in the Indian education system in 21st century. Educators, administrators, parents and stakeholders play a crucial role in creating an inclusive environment. The National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020) envisions equal learning opportunities for all students, regardless of inherent and societal obstacles. The objectives of equity and inclusion in education in India are multifaceted, aiming to address disparities and promote inclusive growth across various socio-economic and cultural dimensions. NEP 2020 and Constitutional provisions emphasize equitable and inclusive education in order to focus on marginalized communities, children with disabilities, and gender discrimination. Hence, it becomes very important to sensitize the stakeholders and enhance teacher capabilities to address the learning needs of students so that the social and gender gaps can be filled.

Keywords Equity, Inclusion, Education, Administration.

Introduction

Equity and inclusion in education refers to the principle or policy that provides equal access for all learners to curriculum and programming within an educational setting. Some school boards have policies that include the terms inclusion and diversity.

Equity and inclusion policy provide a framework for educators and academic administrators that guides training and delivery of instruction and programming. School boards use equity and inclusion principles to promote the use of resources that reflect the diversity of students and their needs.

In the past, equity and inclusion referred primarily to students with mental and/or physical challenges that prevented them from learning in regular classrooms. The principle now applies to marginalized students who live with any type of intersectionality based on their social identity.

Inclusion speaks to the qualitative experience that students have. Inclusion means students are able to express their authentic selves in the learning space and still have access to all learning opportunities.

Objective of study

1. To study the role of equity and inclusion in the Indian Education System.
2. To examine the visions of NEP 2020 regarding equitable and inclusive education for the students.
3. To explore the key recommendations of NEP 2020 for equity and inclusion.

Review of Literature

Singh, Rathi et al. (2023) did an exploratory study on the Indian education system and revealed that social equity in the Indian Education System can be improved through policy reforms, increased funding, community involvement, and social justice principles.

Singh & Mishra (2023) in their study systematically reviewed the NEP 2020 and the Indian Constitution to support equitable and inclusive education. They found the

challenges in resource allocation and ensuring equitable distribution need to be addressed for effective implementation.

Bhat & Geelani (2018) in their study found that Inclusive Education in India faces different types of challenges like a lack of positive attitudes among teachers, a non-inclusive curriculum, and infrastructure issues. But, after overcoming these types of obstacles can lead to equal opportunities for all learners in India.

Mukhopadhyay & Sriprakash (2013) in their research paper critically examined how inclusion and equity are constituted through education development policies in India. They conducted an ethnographic study and found that target-driven approaches to education for all produced narrow understandings of equity.

Main Text

Equity In Education

1. Equity refers to the concept of providing fair access to programming and learning opportunities based on the differing needs of each student. Equality refers to all students having access to programming and learning opportunities.
2. Equity in education means that personal or social circumstances such as gender, ethnic origin or family background, are not obstacles to achieving educational potential (definition of fairness) and that all individuals reach at least a basic minimum level of skills (definition of inclusion). In these education systems, the vast majority of students have the opportunity to attain high-level skills, regardless of their own personal and socio-economic circumstances.

Concept of Equity and Equality

There is a common misconception about the differences between Equity and Equality in the areas of education, health, sports, opportunities etc. The two terms are used interchangeably as we assume that equity is same as equality, but the truth is that they are different.

1. Equity denotes subjective and ethical judgement whereas equality is more objective.
2. Equity is a means whereas equality is an end.
3. Equity is a process while equality is the outcome of that process. That's why equity is the necessary condition to be fulfilled to achieve equality.
4. In equity, the differences are recognized and so efforts are made to treat everyone differently. On the contrary, equality recognizes sameness and so it aims at treating everyone equally.

5. Justness and fairness in the manner of treating individuals are called equity. Equality is a state or situation where everyone is at the same level.

Principles of Ensuring Equity in Education

1. Raise awareness and work towards an achievement of equity
2. Listen to the Children and Their parents.
3. Work with civil society organizations that have connections with community.
4. Setup a system for watching over the school and community to address discrimination.
5. Accept that certain children are excluded from participating equitably in education.

Six dimensions of Educational Equity

Inclusion in Education

1. Inclusive education means providing equal opportunities to all the learners whether disabled or disabled in a regular classroom setting. In an inclusion setting all students learn together and main emphasis is on the abilities of the learners rather than disabilities. In inclusive education all the learners equally participate in curricular and co curricular activities. In an inclusive environment children with special needs spend most of their time with normal children.
2. Inclusive education is concerned with providing appropriate responses to the broad spectrum of learning needs in formal and non-formal educational settings. Rather than being a marginal theme on how some learners can be integrated in the mainstream education, inclusive education is an approach that investigates how to transform education systems in order to respond to the diversity of learners. It aims to enable both teachers and learners to feel comfortable with diversity and to see it as a challenge and enrichment in the learning environment, rather than a problem.

Representation of Inclusive education

Definition of Inclusive Education

1. According to Stainback (1992), "Inclusion facilitates integration in school systems when general and special education personnel, as well as curriculum and instructional procedures, are combined to provide educational experiences to meet the needs of the students in an integrated setup."
2. According to UNESCO (1994), "Inclusion is seen as diversity of needs of all learners through increasing participation a process of addressing and responding to the in learning, cultures and communities, and reducing exclusion within and from education (Booth, 1996). It involves changes and modifications in content, approaches, structures and strategies, with a common vision which covers all children of the appropriate age range and a conviction that it is the responsibility of the regular system to educate all children."

Aims and Objective of Inclusive Education

The aim is to identify and enrol children with disabilities in regular schools, to provide them with effective academic support and to provide them with the knowledge on how to face the challenges in and around the society they are a part of.

1. **Education of all:** It is giving all children in the same classroom in the same school get real learning opportunities that have been excluded. An inclusive school aims to meet everyone's educational needs by having them supported by their peers and other members of the school community. Children with disabilities demonstrates high level of social inter action with non-disabled peers in an inclusive setting compared to segregated setting. Children with disabilities in inclusive setting often have a more vigorous educational program in improving their skills and academics gains. Normal children get the benefit from improved instructional technologies, in the classrooms. All the children will be given equal opportunity and an equal chance to learn to the best of their abilities, the devices in the classrooms should meet the special education needs.

2. **Protection of rights:** Protect the rights to education of person with disabilities and also giving the right to education of person with disabilities. The Indian Constitution guarantees equality, freedom, justice, and dignity to all individual and mandates an inclusive society that comprises people with disabilities. Inclusive education aims to strengthen the human dignity and to remove many stereotypes from each other's mind and accept the fact that nobody is perfect. In 1974 the Government of India launched the Integrated Education for Disabled Children scheme (IEDC) in 1987 the Project Integrated Education (PIED) for disabled. The District Primary Education Program (DPEP) with aims to move towards "universalization of elementary education". The objective of integrated education for disabled children scheme (IEDC Scheme) was to provide educational opportunities for disabled children in common schools to facilitate their retention in the school system, to also integrate the disabled children with the general community at all levels as equal partners and to prepare them for normal growth and to face life with courage and confidence.

3. **Identification of skills:** The skills in inclusive education includes following instructions given by the teacher obeying classroom rules and skills in problem solving and self care. Inclusive education promotes the social value of equality; inclusive setting leads to independent thoughts, positive competency and improved self-esteem. All the children are enriched by the opportunity in which they learn and care for each other and hence gain the skills and values needed for community living. Inclusive Education also aims to give disable pupils the opportunity to become a part of the school community, and also get a realistic idea of what a multiform and competitive society looks like as their own possibilities and limitations.

4. **Development of social consciousness:** Social consciousness and social action are decidedly associated with education since it is there in that, both specific cognitive abilities and attitude to social reality are largely developed. Emotionally disturbed children are those that, in terms of their emotional make-up and behavior, depart significantly and persistently from the majority of children of their age and social group, negatively influencing their adjustment to their self and social surroundings.

5. **To prepare for new challenges:** To engage every student, teachers must be innovative in their instruction. Everyone's expectation for children's inclusion and admiration throughout their lives is reflected in inclusive education. Every youngster may take part in their community, feel a feeling of belonging, and be better equipped for adulthood. Children have a range of skills, and as a result, they have diverse reasons for wanting to learn in a classroom with their classmates. The child's abilities and talents can be developed through successful inclusion efforts.

6. **Development of brotherhood:** Children come from a variety of origins, and while they may differ from one another in terms of their physical prowess, mental prowess, and even learning preferences, they still share in all the privileges. Children learn to respect both their own and other people's originality. When they cultivate tolerance, patience, and compassion for their fellow students, students raise their emotional intelligence. They get the ability to tolerate the positives and negatives of others. Children who assist their peers often develop friendships that last a lifetime in addition to receiving great satisfaction from doing so.

7. **To improve the quality of education:** All children receive higher-quality education thanks to inclusive systems, which also play a crucial role in eradicating prejudice. Schools offer the setting for a child's first encounter with the world outside of their families, facilitating the growth of social bonds and interactions. Students with different skills and backgrounds play, interact, and study together, which fosters respect and understanding. With segregated and exclusive education, historically oppressed communities continue to face prejudice.

Importance of Inclusive education

Principles of Inclusive Education

1. **No Discrimination with students:** There should be no discrimination in educational institutions, the students should be equally treated regardless of social background, race,

gender, religion, Children with disabilities must be able to access education without discrimination and on the basis of equality. This means the right not to be segregated, and to be provided with all the support they need. All barriers must be removed - legal, physical, communication and language, social, financial and attitudinal barriers.

2. Equal Education opportunity to all: There should be equality of opportunity in education, where everyone has fair and equal access to a good quality education regardless of being disabled, social background, race, gender or religion, and where people achieve success in education according to their efforts and ability, free of any form of discrimination.

3. The students view are listened to and taken seriously: Children have the right to be able to express their views on all matters affecting them and to have those views taken seriously, in accordance with the child's age and maturity. This does not mean that you must do whatever children want. However it does mean that their feelings, concerns and ideas should be taken into account when you are making decisions about them especially in school. This involves both listening and taking on board what the children say.

4. School adapt to the need of students: Inclusive education provides such learning environment that promotes all round development of all learners together in the same educational settings. The content, the teaching process, assessment and evaluation, and the physical environment may be modified to help students to achieve success in the classroom

5. Individual differences between students are a source of richness and diversity, and not a problem: Adjusting the learning environment according to the individual needs of the student and preparing the curricular by considering these individual differences will help the development of individuals. It is very important for a teacher to understand the individual differences of each and every learner so that effective teaching-learning takes place. A teacher should understand the various psychological, personal, social, religious, and other factors within the classroom. A teacher should decide teaching-learning strategies according to the individual differences of students in the class. Develop a curriculum that suits the needs of individual differences needs. Consider the individual differences of the class and construct the environment in such a way so that it provides equal opportunities to all.

Principles of Inclusive education

Merits of Inclusive Education

1. Friendly attitude: A positive or friendly attitude towards students is something that goes deeper and has an effect beyond surface cheer while showing a negative attitude promotes fear. To be disabled or having a disability can also affect an individual's mental health so by displaying a friendly attitude like smiling, kind behavior, showing empathy, patience and positive attitude towards the students promotes in inclusion and openness for the affected individual.

When it comes to school, an individual's mental attitude plays a role not just in how others perceive, but on one's performance. Inclusive Education can only grow and develop in a system, which generates positive or friendly attitude.

2. Increased social initiations, relationships and networks: Individuals with disability often show low levels of social engagement and low social affect. By embedding social interaction in inclusive education, individuals who are having a disability may be more motivated to seek out and engage with other people.

- Having a positive social interactions have a wide range of both physical and mental benefits of an individual like increased cognitive ability, a good mental health, communication skills, being independent, and helps in improving their physical health. By increasing more positive initiations can also help an individual to develop strong language skills, creativity, empathy, communication, and confidence.

- Promoting a good relationship between peers is very important to ensure the success of inclusion of an individual with disability.

- Inclusive learning environments provide students having a disability with many opportunities to establish relationships with their peers. Relationships form the beginnings of friendships that are a source of fun and enjoyment, and an essential source of emotional support during challenging times and it contributes most to one's quality of life. Therefore, the opportunity to connect with a diverse group of peers is an important outcome of inclusion for all students.

3. Peer role models for academic, social and behaviour skills: Peer modelling is another support that can be used to help students to learn academic, processes and classroom routines. It also provides the classroom teacher opportunities to use peers to assist with instruction, clarifying directions and give social reminders with little or no disruption to the lesson cycle.

4. Increased achievement of IEP goals: A good IEP (Individualized Education Programme) will clearly present levels of performance for the student and offer insight into how to best use their strengths and interests to improve the areas they are weakest. Then the focus will shift to problem areas that need to be addressed and the learning goals that the plan needs to cover like: Academic skills

- Communication development
- Emotional/social skills
- Increase independence
- Demonstrate personal awareness and control

Greater access to the general curriculum: Access to the general curriculum means providing students with disabilities meaning being involved in and progress in the general curriculum can be viewed as providing specific details about how the concept of access is to be achieved. Therefore like: IEP goals must address how the student will be involved in and progress in the general curriculum; The IEP must specify appropriate supplementary aids and services, accommodations, modifications, or supports; and The IEP must include an explanation if the student will not participate in the regular class.

Conclusion

NEP, 2020 for Equity and Inclusion

1. The National Education Policy (NEP), 2020 emphasizes that, "Education is the single greatest tool for achieving social justice and equality" which has implications for development of an inclusive community and society at large. In order for policy to translate to practice, educational barriers, facilities and services for Children with Special Needs (CwSN) must be addressed.
2. The NEP has infused the aspects of disability inclusion throughout the policy document with a dedicated chapter on equitable and inclusive education, focusing on issues, challenges and recommendations for bridging the gaps reducing the disparities in access and participation of all learners.
3. The issues and recommendations for inclusion of underrepresented students groups including children with disabilities has been subsumed in the policy and covered under the SEDGs i.e. Socio-Economically Disadvantaged Groups (SEDGs) which is an umbrella term covering gender identities, socio-cultural and socioeconomic identities, geographical identities as well as disabilities.
4. The Policy advocates the provisions for CwSN as per the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (RPwD) Act, 2016. Inclusive education broadly encompasses the teaching-learning environment which is welcoming and supports all learners regardless of learning styles, abilities and disabilities.
5. The Centrally sponsored scheme of Samagra Shiksha, is an integrated scheme of the Ministry of Education for school education catering from pre-primary to senior secondary classes. The scheme aims to universalize access to school education and supports all States and UTs in implementing the recommendations of the NEP.

Ensuring equity and inclusion at all levels of school education is one of the major objectives of the scheme.

- The Ministry of Education is facilitating inclusive quality school education for children with special needs through various ventures and initiatives. Dedicated efforts for student learning support have been undertaken by NCERT such as ePathshala portal.

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